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Research Article

**GILBERT'S SYNDROME-A RARE CASE PRESENTATION:
CASE STUDY**¹*Dr. Zahra Noor, ²Dr. Sunera Qadeer, ³Dr. Moattar Asmat¹Allama Iqbal Medical Collage, LHR, zhaimc123@gmail.com, 0092-3204835679²Allama Iqbal Medical Collage, LHR, 0092-3324995634³Allama Iqbal Medical Collage, LHR, moatterasmat@gmail.com, 0092-3330761314**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Gilbert syndrome is benign, often familial condition characterized by recurrent but asymptomatic mild unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia in the absence of hemolysis or underlying liver disease. If, it becomes apparent, it is not until adolescence and then usually in association with stress such as intercurrent illness, fasting or strenuous exercise. We hereby report a case of 33 year old male presented with history of recurrent episodes of mild jaundice, anorexia and abdominal pain. Liver function tests showed raised unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia and normal SGPT, serum alkalinephosphatase, serum albumin and prothrombin time. Hemolysis was excluded by normal hemoglobin, peripheral blood film and reticulocyte count and finally he was diagnosed to have Gilbert's syndrome. Patient was reassured about self-resolving nature of this benign condition.

Keywords: Gilbert Syndrome, familial non-hemolytic jaundice, hereditary non-hemolytic hyperbilirubinaemia,

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INTRODUCTION:

Gilbert's syndrome (GS) is an autosomal recessive inherited disorder of bilirubin glucuronidation characterized by unconjugated hyperbilirubinaemia in the absence of hepatocellular injury or hemolysis [1,2]. GS has a worldwide distribution. Overall GS is found in approximately 3–10% of the general population [3,4]. GS is present at birth, but may remain undiagnosed until the second decade of life where subjects develop mild hyperbilirubinaemia or may present with fluctuating overt jaundice [4].

Gilbert syndrome may be precipitated by dehydration, fasting menstrual periods or stress, such as an intercurrent illness or vigorous exercise [5]. Patients may complain of vague abdominal discomfort and general fatigue for which no cause is found. These episodes resolve spontaneously and no treatment is required except for supportive care [6].

CASE REPORT:

A 33 year old man from a small city of Pakistan presented with complaint of mild jaundice associated with anorexia, malaise, fatigue and abdominal discomfort. There were no complaints of fever, diarrhea and vomiting. Urine color was normal. He reported similar event at age of 12 years first time and then at age of 18 years and 32 years that subsides on its own without treatment and no labs were done during previous episodes. On physical examination, mild jaundice present, no other abnormal physical findings were evident. Investigations done revealed Liver function tests were all within normal limit including HBsAg and Anti HCV, SGPT, SGOT, serum alkalinephosphatase, serum albumin and prothrombin time with the exception of unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia. The total and indirect serum bilirubin levels were 3mg/dl and 2.2mg/dl respectively. There was normal hemoglobin (13.5 g/dl), total and differential count ESR and adequate platelets. Reticulocyte was within normal limit (0.5%). Peripheral blood picture showed no abnormality including any features of hemolysis. Osmotic fragility done was within normal limit. A diagnosis of gilbert syndrome was made and patient reassured about this benign condition and counseled regarding avoiding factors that may cause jaundice and symptoms. His condition improved within few days after conservative management both clinically and biochemically.

DISCUSSION:

Unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia in Gilbert syndrome has long been recognized as due to under activity of the conjugating enzyme system Uridine diphosphate glucuronosyltransferase (UDPGT). Bilirubin UDPGT is responsible for

conjugating bilirubin into bilirubin monoglucuronides and diglucuronides and is located primarily in the endoplasmic reticulum of hepatocytes. The UGT1 gene locus for Gilbert syndrome is located on chromosome 2 and is responsible for virtually all bilirubin conjugation [7]. Gilbert syndrome is a benign condition with no associated morbidity or mortality affecting all races occurring predominantly in men with a male to female ratio ranging from 2:1-7:1 [4]. It usually is diagnosed around puberty, possibly due to inhibition of bilirubin glucuronidation by endogenous steroid hormones. In older subjects, the diagnosis is usually made when unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia is noted on routine blood tests or unmasked by an intercurrent illness or stress.

Bilirubin levels are most often <3 mg/dl. Deepening may follow an intercurrent infection or fasting and is associated with malaise, nausea and often discomfort over liver [4,5]. There is no other abnormal physical sign.

Diagnosis of Gilbert syndrome can be made in the presence of (1) unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia noted on several occasions; (2) normal results on CBC, reticulocyte count, and blood smear; (3) normal liver function test results; and absence of other disease processes [8]. Additional tests are rarely required for a diagnosis as it is straightforward.

However, following investigations are performed occasionally to confirm a diagnosis of Gilbert syndrome.

- Fasting: This usually results in a 2- to 3- fold rise in plasma unconjugated bilirubin within 48 hours of a fast that returns to normal levels within 24 hours of resuming a normal diet. Although unconjugated bilirubin levels also rise with fasting in patients with haemolysis or liver disease, the magnitude of the rise is less than that observed with Gilbert syndrome [5,6].
- Nicotinic acid: Intravenous administration of 50 mg of nicotinic acid results in a 2-to3- fold rise in plasma unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia within 3 hours.
- Phenobarbital: Phenobarbital and other enzyme inducers of the bilirubin-UDPGT system will normalize plasma bilirubin in patients with Gilbert syndrome.
- Rifampicin test: This test is popular because of non-invasive in nature. It is as reliable as fasting test. Per oral administration of 600-900 mg of rifampicin results in rise in plasma unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia within 2-4 hours [9].
- Thin-layer chromatography: This test is diagnostic for Gilbert syndrome when it shows a significantly higher proportion of unconjugated bilirubin when compared to individuals with

chronic haemolysis, liver disease or those who are healthy. If confirmation of the diagnosis is truly essential, chromatographic determination is of potential use. This will show an increased ratio of bilirubin monoglucuronide to diglucuronide, reflecting reduced bilirubin-UDPGT activity.

• Polymerase chain reaction: The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is a novel and rapid method of identifying genetic polymorphisms in the TATA box of the UDPGT1 gene using fluorescence resonance energy transfer.

Gilbert's syndrome has an excellent prognosis. Patients have a normal life expectancy and reassurance is the only necessary treatment [10]. Hyperbilirubinaemia is life long and not associated with increased morbidity. Serum bilirubin may be reduced by phenobarbitone but, as jaundice is rarely obvious, few patients will get cosmetic benefit from this treatment. Patients should be warned that jaundice can follow an intercurrent infection, repeated vomiting or missed meals [11,12].

Gilbert syndrome has long been described as an asymptomatic disorder that does not have clinical implications and no monitoring is recommended. However, some studies showed that the quality of life in GS subjects is affected particularly during the jaundice episodes [4,13]. Subjects with GS need special care in specific conditions such as surgery, anesthesia, weight loss plans design, prescription of medicines [4,11].

CONCLUSION:

In the light of above case, if a patient comes with isolated unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia (< 6 mg/dl) on several occasions in the absence of hemolysis or underlying liver disease; Gilbert syndrome should be entertained in the differential diagnosis of unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia. It has no deleterious associations and an excellent prognosis, and those who have it can lead a normal lifestyle. Subjects with GS need to be well informed of the risk factors for exacerbation of hyperbilirubinemia and avoid such factors. Subjects with GS need special care in specific conditions such as surgery, anesthesia, weight loss plans design, prescription of medicines.

CONSENT:

The consent was taken and signed by the respected patient.

REFERENCES:

1. Fretzayas A, Moustaki M, Liapi O, Karpathios T. Gilbert syndrome. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2012; 171(11).
2. Gazzin S, Masutti F, Vitek L, Tiribelli C. The molecular basis of jaundice: an old symptom revisited. *Liver Int.* 2017;37(8): 1094–102

3. Monaghan G, McLellan A, McGeehan A, et al. Gilbert's syndrome is a contributory factor in prolonged unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia of the newborn. *J Pediatr.* 1999;134:441–6
4. S. Kamal, S. Abdelhakam, D. Ghoraba, et al., "The frequency, clinical course, and health related quality of life in adults with Gilbert's syndrome: a longitudinal study", *BMC Gastroenterol* **19**, 22 (2019) doi: 10.1186/s12876-019-0931-2.
5. E. Flores-Villalba, C. Rodriguez-Montalvo, G. Arredondo-Saldaña, "Unusual presentation of Gilbert disease with high levels of unconjugated bilirubin. Report of two cases" *Archives Medical Review Journal*, 2016; 108(4)
6. Manandhar, S. Raja, Baral, et al., "A case report of Gilbert Syndrome. Kathmandu University medical journal (KUMJ)", 2003; 1: 187-9.
7. Lee JS, Wang J, Martin M, et al. Genetic variation in UGT1A1 typical of Gilbert syndrome is associated with unconjugated hyperbilirubinemia in patients receiving tocilizumab. *Pharmacogenet Genomics.* 2011;21: 365–74.
8. K. Wagner, R. G. Sheils, C. Anna, et al., "Diagnostic criteria and contributors to Gilbert's syndrome", *J. Critical Reviews in Clinical Laboratory Sciences* :2018 Feb; 55(2): 129-139.
9. Erdil A, Kadayifci A, Ates Y, Bagci S, Uygun A, Dagalp K. Rifampicin test in the diagnosis of Gilbert's syndrome. *Int J Clin Pract.* 2001; 55(2):81–3.
10. Wazib, Hossain, Saha JK, et al., "A Case of Gilbert's Syndrome", *J Dhaka Med Coll.* 2010; 19(1): 67-68.
11. Ahsan Rasool, Sabir Sabir, Muhammad Ashfaq et al., "Gilbert's syndrome-A Concealed Adversity for Physicians and Surgeons", *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*, 2015;27(3): 707-710.
12. L. C. Claridge et al., "Gilbert's syndrome", *BMJ* 2011; 342: d2293
13. E. Cüre, Erkan, S. Yüce, M. Cüre, "Gilbert's Syndrome", *Archives Medical Review Journal*, 2014 April; 220- 236.